

MODELLING AND SIMULATION OF A STANDALONE WIND TURBINE SYSTEM USING MATLAB/SIMULINK FOR PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION

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Abstract

The increasing demand for clean and decentralized energy solutions has driven interest in small-scale renewable energy systems, particularly for standalone and off-grid applications. However, optimizing wind turbine parameters for optimum performance could be challenging. Also, physical prototyping without prior simulation may lead to increased costs and inefficiencies. This study presents a MATLAB/Simulink-based model of a 5 kW standalone wind turbine system to facilitate comprehensive performance analysis and optimization before implementation. The developed model used power coefficient and tip speed ratio formulations to evaluate the effects of key design parameters. Simulation was performed and the influence of turbine speed, rotor radius, pitch angle and wind speed on mechanical power and torque was analyzed. The results reveal that to achieve 5 kW rated mechanical power when the wind speed and pitch angle are 12 ms⁻¹ and 0 respectively, the value of turbine radius, turbine speed and optimal tip speed ratio is 1.9143 m, 50.775 rad/s and 8.098 respectively. Turbine speeds of 40 ms⁻¹ and 60 ms⁻¹ have the mechanical power of 3.62 kW and 2.78 kW respectively at constant windspeed of 12m/s. Wind speed of 21.60 ms⁻¹ gives the maximum power of 11.64 kW. Any increment beyond 21.60 m/s will make mechanical power declines. This indicates that wind speed has great impact on power generation. The model gives the designers leverage to determine the optimal parameters for efficient and reliable wind turbine system. This study provides validated platform for design prototyping and academic research.

Keywords

wind turbine,
standalone energy
system,
renewable energy,
power coefficient,
tip speed ratio

1. INTRODUCTION

The universal concern toward sustainable and decentralized energy generation system has increased the acceptance of renewable energy technologies, particularly in faraway and off-grid locations [1]. Among these, wind energy stands out as a mature and feasible option due to its scalability and relatively low environmental impact. Small-scale standalone wind turbines are increasingly being deployed in rural communities, islanded microgrids, and agricultural facilities where connection to the central grid is either impractical or cost-prohibitive [2]. However, the performance of a wind energy conversion system (WECS) is inherently nonlinear and depends on several interrelated parameters, including wind speed, rotor radius, turbine speed, and pitch angle [3]. These variables directly influence the aerodynamic and mechanical power outputs of the turbine [4]. Poor understanding or neglect of their interactions often results in suboptimal designs, leading to energy inefficiency, mechanical stress, or premature failure. Physical prototyping of wind turbines without prior simulation is both costly and time-consuming [5]. Therefore, developing accurate simulation models is essential for design verification and performance analysis. MATLAB/Simulink offers a flexible and robust platform for modeling dynamic systems and evaluating control strategies under various conditions. It has been estimated that about 650 million people in Africa do not have access to electricity [6]. Adequate investment in renewable energy as a source of electricity could bridge the gap of unaffordability and inaccessibility of electrical energy in the region. About 75% of the sub-sahara populace do not have access to electricity. 500 million of these population reside in rural areas. Renewable energy through off-grid mini-grid could be deployed to mitigate the problem of unavailability of electricity [7]. Mini-grids are independent electrical networks of electrical loads which are powered by

independent electrical sources. They have power ratings up to 10 MW and can flexibly operate in stand-alone and grid-connected modes. Three forms of mini-grids can be identified in the literature: fossil-based mini-grids, renewable-based mini-grids, and hybrid renewable mini-grids [8]. Mini-grids could be deployed to remote areas at an affordable cost if renewable energy resources are incorporated [9]. It is estimated that nearly 60% of Africans reside in rural communities, and approximately 5% of these people have access to clean electricity. One of the major causes of low electrification rates in rural communities is the proximity to the existing grid infrastructure, sparsely distributed settlements and low population density, and the presence of low socio-economic activities.

With the rapid growth of global energy, climate change is increasingly concerning. In this regard, the use of clean and renewable energy is increasingly underscored. As a clean renewable energy source, offshore wind energy is receiving particular attention from many countries, and numerous relevant studies and projects have been conducted [10]. Critical to extending electricity access to these remote communities is the deployment of mini-grid technologies. As such, electrification policies are now redirecting focus to the proliferation of mini-grid facilities not only for the rural communities but also for the peri-urban and urban areas that are underserved [11]. It is said that Africa is home to a large number of planned mini-grid initiatives globally. Data available from World Bank indicate that over 4,000 mini-grid facilities are currently in the planning stage on the continent [12]. Among the renewable energy resources, wind energy has a greater advantage of being pollution-free, clean and sustainable [13]. However, according to the Global Wind Energy Outlook presented by the Global Wind Energy Council, the utilization rate of wind resources is still generally low [14].

Figure 1 show the countries that have installed capacity of more than 10 GW using wind energy. China has the largest installed capacity of 282 GW, then United States of America with 118 GW installed capacity.

Figure 1. Global wind power capacity [15]

Nigeria has the energy resources for its development. Now, it needs the infrastructure to access them. From hydropower to gas, solar and wind, the continent holds the world’s largest untapped energy resources. But, the potential to support energy at scale remains unrealized. In 2024, only 6.5 GW of new grid capacity was added, far behind peers like India (18 GW from renewables alone) and the US with over 48 GW. The problem is not potential, it is infrastructure. The 2025 State of Africa’s Infrastructure Report shows that without better transmission and integration, energy stays isolated. With it, the continent can unlock the most resilient, interconnected energy market in the world [16]. [17] in their study size the important components of hybridized renewable energy system using HOMER software. The study performed technical, financial evaluation, renewable factor, estimate the harmful emissions, and sensitivity analysis. [18] identified the most critical parameters in a complex utility-scale solar PV plant model using a modified Sobol’ sensitivity analysis. By pinpointing these key parameters, validated on standard IEEE test systems, the research significantly simplifies dynamic grid studies. This helps transmission system planners focus on the most impactful factors, improving the efficiency and reliability of integrating solar PV into bulk power systems. [19] optimized a decentralized hybrid renewable energy system to meet the large electrical and thermal demands of a complex facility. Using HOMER and MATLAB, 1,945 Pareto-optimal

configurations were identified, balancing cost, reliability, and environmental impact. The most effective configuration combined PV, fuel cell, electrolyzer, hydrogen tank, battery, inverter, and partial grid power (20%).

[20] evaluated the effects of the operation of a 5-MW wind turbine in non-ideal conditions on the fatigue of its main components considering the wind resource in two locations; one in the northeast of Brazil and another on the North Sea, in Europe. The open-source software for wind turbine simulation OpenFAST were employed for numerical simulations in their study. [21] modelled and evaluated the performance analysis of a standalone wind system in MATLAB/SIMULINK environment. The maximum power generated was 479.8 W at 16m/s and the minimum power generated was 202.5 W at 12m/s. Though, The optimal values of the turbine radius, its speed and tip speed ratio were not reported. [22] also modelled and simulated a standalone wind energy conversion system for small scale operations. The developed system delivers a power of 2.25 kW which would be enough for a lighting up a few houses in remote areas. The effect of wind speed, turbine radius and pitch angle on the output power were not considered. [23] employed an artificial neural network (ANN) technique in adjusting turbine's tip speed ratio (TSR) for power quality enhancement. TSR variations from 0 to 25 radians, the mechanical power output using the traditional classical control (TCC) method becomes stable at 240 W level, 58.33% improvement in the stability responses obtained. The study did not consider the relationship between wind turbine parameters.

The aim of this study is to design, model and evaluate a 5 kW wind turbine using MATLAB/Simulink. The objectives of this study are to:

- (a) to develop a MATLAB/Simulink model of a 5 kW wind turbine system.
- (b) to evaluate the mechanical power output and torque as functions of wind speed, pitch angle, rotor radius, and turbine speed.
- (c) to analyze the impact of each parameter on turbine performance for optimal design conditions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Wind Turbine Mathematical Modelling

Equation (1) represents the mathematical model of a wind turbine. The equation was employed to developed the model in MATLAB/Simulink as shown in Figure 2. Equation (2) shows that the power coefficient is a function of tip speed ratio and pitch angle. Equations (3) and (4) represent the intermittent tip speed ratio and tip speed ratio respectively.

$$P_t = \frac{1}{2} C_p \rho A V^3 \tag{1}$$

P_t = Power extracted by the wind turbine (W)

V = Wind speed (m/s)

A = Rotor area (m²)

ρ = Air density (kg/m³)

C_p = Power coefficient (2)

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = C_1 \times \left(\frac{C_2}{\lambda_i} - C_3\beta - C_4\beta^2 - C_5 \right) \times e^{-\frac{C_6}{\lambda}}$$

$C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5,$ and C_6 are constant

λ = tip speed ratio

λ_i = intermittent tip speed ratio

β = pitch angle

$C_1 = 0.5, C_2 = 116, C_3 = 0.4, C_4 = 0, C_5 = 5, C_6 = 21$ [24]

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i} = \frac{1}{\lambda_T + 0.08\beta} - \frac{0.035}{\beta^3 + 1} \tag{3}$$

$$\lambda = \lambda_T^{op} = \frac{\omega_T \times r_T}{V_w} \tag{4}$$

ω_T = speed of the turbine blade (rad/s)

r_T = blade radius (m)

V_w = wind speed (m/s)

In order to obtain the intermittent TSR and TSR of the wind turbine, Equation (2) and (3) were modelled in MATLAB/Simulink environment as shown in Figure 3. Figure 4 shows the final wind turbine model developed in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. Inputs parameters to the wind turbine are turbine radius, wind speed, pitch angle and turbine speed. The output parameters of the wind turbine are mechanical power and torque. The optimal values of the inputs parameters were determined for the turbine to produce a 5 kW mechanical power [25].

Figure 2: Modelling of TSR and intermittent TSR of wind turbine system

Figure 3: Modelling of wind turbine power coefficient

Figure 4: Model of the wind turbine

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Power coefficient, C_p , and intermittent TSR are 0.4105 and 11.30 respectively as shown in Figure 5. Also, the optimal TSR for the wind turbine to generate 5 kW mechanical output power is 8.098 is illustrated in Figure 6. The optimal turbine radius for 5 kW mechanical power as shown in Figure 6 is 1.9193 m. Though, increment in the turbine radius could increase the mechanical power output as illustrated in Figure 7. The maximum attained mechanical power is 6061.50 W with the corresponding turbine radius of 2.29 m. Likewise, to generate 5 kW power the optimal windspeed is 12 m/s as presented in Figure 8. Increment in the windspeed will lead to increment in the mechanical power up to the maximum mechanical power of 11.64 kW with corresponding windspeed of 21.60 m/s. Any increment beyond 21.60 m/s windspeed will cause decrement in the output mechanical power. Figures 9 and 10 showed that the optimal pitch angle and turbine speed are 0° and 50.775 rad/s respectively. Any increment in the both parameters, the pitch angle and the turbine speed will lead to decrease in the output mechanical power of the wind turbine.

five_kw_wind_turbine_design ▶ Wind turbine ▶ Equations 2 and 3

Figure 5: Variation of C_p and TSR with pitch angle

Figure 6: Optimal TSR of the wind turbine

Figure 7: Optimal performance of the turbine blade radius

Figure 8: Optimal performance of the wind speed

Figure 9: Optimal performance of the pitch angle

Figure 10: Optimal performance of the turbine speed

For the wind turbine to generate mechanical power of 5 kW, the optimal turbine radius, windspeed, pitch angle and turbine speed are 1.9139 m, 12 m/s, 0° and 50.775 rad/s respectively as shown in Figure 11. The corresponding torque is 253.9 kNm. These parameters have direct effect on the mechanical power and torque of the wind turbine

Figure 11: Optimal wind speed turbine

4. CONCLUSION

The results reveal that to achieve 5 kW rated mechanical power when the wind speed and pitch angle are 12 m/s and 0 respectively, the value of turbine radius, turbine speed and optimal tip speed ratio is 1.9139 m, 50.775 rad/s and 8.12 m/s respectively. This indicates that wind speed has great impact on power generation. The model gives the designers leverage to determine the optimal parameters for efficient and reliable wind turbine system. This study provides a validated platform for design prototyping and academic research.

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